

Digital Mobilizer App: An App to Introduce Basic Environmental Education and Motivate Population Engagement in Sustainable Development through Personas Created by Waste Pickers

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Abstract

This paper presents the conception phase of the Digital Mobilizer App (DMA), an Information Module component of the Egalitarian project EcoLink project, part of the ERASMUS+ program funded by the EU. DMA aims to develop a mobile application to introduce basic environmental education and encourage engagement in sustainable development. The app features AI-generated personas created by waste pickers to represent themselves and their children, fostering inclusion and representation in educational initiatives. The paper consolidates the workshop results conducted during the Waste Summit Brasília 2025, involving ten CENTCOOP waste pickers, an entity representing over a dozen of waste picker cooperatives. The workshop, conducted by AAU, Saxion, and UnB students, supervised by UnB professors, utilized an AI-powered program from Educado, another Egalitarian project, to create personas based on participants' inputs. Waste pickers identified contamination as their main problem, alongside with hospital waste, low-quality recyclables, organic matter, and even animal corpses. They also highlighted the need for systemic improvements, including fines, external education, and awareness campaigns. The waste pickers suggested AI-generated child personas as influencers. The findings underscore strong participant engagement, with waste pickers expressing satisfaction with the personas, linking them to real individuals in their cooperatives. The study highlights the potential of AI-driven participatory design to empower marginalized communities, enhance their visibility, and support advocacy efforts. UnB's professors and students presented the results to another cooperative, which demonstrated strong interest in future workshops. The major reference for DMA during 2025 is the P3RD Model (P-Prevention, R₁-Reduction, R₂-Reuse, R₃-Recycling, D-Disposal), adaptation of the 10R Dutch Circular Economy Model. Within the scope of cooperatives of waste pickers, DMA will focus on Selective Collection, Triage/Sorting, Transformation, and Commercialization (C₁T₁T₂C₂), aligned with Reuse (R₂-Reuse) and Recycling (R₃-Recycling) components of the P3RD model.

Keywords: Digital Mobilizer; Personas Created by Waste pickers; Personas of Waste Pickers; Environmental Education; Population Engagement; Interest Groups; Waste Summit Brasília 2025.

1 Introduction

Environmental education plays a fundamental role in promoting sustainable development, especially when associated with initiatives that directly engage marginalized communities (Tilbury, 2011). The Digital Mobilizer App (DMA) emerges as an innovative tool within the EcoLink project, part of the Erasmus+ program funded by the European Union, aiming to foster environmental awareness and encourage community participation in sustainable practices (European Commission, 2020). DMA is aligned with all EcoLink's features: (i) a marketplace, connecting consumers to sustainable companies; (ii) an information hub, with educational content focused on sustainability; (iii) a reuse and recycling section, which facilitates donations and collections of reusable and recyclable materials; and (iv) a community space, dedicated to promoting interactions and events focused on sustainable practices. Thus, DMA plays a major role towards consolidating EcoLink as a tool for social

engagement and environmental awareness, offering an accessible and innovative resource that contributes to the adoption of more responsible habits, in addition to stimulating significant transformations towards a more conscious consumption model. By leveraging artificial intelligence (AI), the app allows waste pickers to create digital personas, enhancing inclusivity and social recognition in educational settings (Gunkel, 2020).

Regarding a major background, the Netherlands created a circular economy system with a vision extending up to 2050, structured around the R10 framework: Refuse, Rethink, Reduce, Reuse, Repair, Refurbish, Remanufacture, Repurpose, Recycle, and Recover Energy (Potting, J., et al., 2017).

DMA aims to explore the potential for adapting the Dutch R10 Model to create a version suitable for developing countries, specifically targeting contexts like Brazil and other developing countries. The project uses a modified model, named the P3RD Model: P= Prevention; R₁= Reduction; R₂= Reuse; R₃= Recycling; and D= Disposal. Besides considering that both, the Solid Waste Disposal into Biodigester Sanitary Landfills and the social-economical inclusion of the waste pickers now making a living in the existing open dumpsites, are relevant elements, this modification simplifies the original framework by focusing on five titles, rather than the ten utilized in the Dutch R10 Model. This adaptation seeks to establish circular economy project management guides tailored to the needs and capacities of developing nations. It is worthwhile to emphasize that all Rs of the Dutch R10 Model are included in the five titles of the P3RD Model: (i) Prevention and Reduction via Product Engineering (PR1) include Refuse, Rethink, Reduce; (ii) Reuse (R₂) encompasses Reuse, Repair, Refurbish, Remanufacture, Repurpose; (iii) Recycling (R₃) that includes only Recycling; and (iv) Disposal (D) into Biodigester Sanitary Landfills, built in such a way to avoid land contamination and allowing industrial use of the methane gas generated.

The DMA's application conceptualization phase was based on a workshop held during the Waste Summit Brasília 2025, which gathered ten waste pickers (seven women and three men) from CENTCOOP, an entity representing over a dozen of waste picker cooperatives (Dias, 2016). The workshop, conducted by researchers and students from UnB, Aalborg University, and Saxion University, provided valuable insights into key environmental challenges, such as waste contamination, hospital waste, poor-quality recyclables, organic waste mismanagement, and even animal carcasses in the recycling stream (Wilson et al., 2012). Furthermore, the waste pickers emphasized the need for systemic improvements, including fines, external education programs, and awareness campaigns (Gutberlet, 2015).

This study builds upon previous research that highlighted the importance of participatory design methods for ensuring the inclusion of marginalized waste pickers in system development (Rahman Rabbi et al., 2024). The Egalitarian Semester Project at AAU demonstrated that participatory methods such as design cards, personas, and scenarios can be successfully used to integrate waste pickers into digital platforms, fostering trust and transparency in waste management system. Inspired by this approach, the DMA project employs AI-generated personas to enhance waste pickers' representation in environmental education.

One of the major innovations of the project is the implementation of AI-generated child personas, suggested by the waste pickers themselves, as influencers in the dissemination of environmental knowledge (Kang et al., 2021). This participatory approach underscores AI's potential in empowering marginalized communities, amplifying their visibility, and supporting their role as key stakeholders in sustainability efforts (Scholz et al., 2018).

The DMA content development in the first semester of 2025 will be based on the Dutch 10R Circular Economy Model, adapted to the P3RD model (P-Prevention, R₁-Reduction, R₂-Reuse, R₃-Recycling, and D-Disposal) (Kirchherr et al., 2017). Within the waste picker cooperatives' context, the app will focus on Selective Collection, Triage/Sorting, Transformation, and Commercialization (C₁T₁T₂C₂), aligning with Reuse (R₂) and Recycling (R₃) principles (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2019).

This paper presents the DMA's conception phase, exploring workshop findings and discussing the potential of AI-driven participatory design to strengthen environmental education and enhance waste pickers' social engagement (Baldé et al., 2017).

2 Summary of the Digital Mobilizer App (DMA) Project

The Digital Mobilizer App (DMA) generator is an innovative digital tool designed to enhance environmental education and promote sustainable development through community engagement (Tilbury, 2011). Developed within the EcoLink project, the DMA generator leverages artificial intelligence (AI) to create digital personas, allowing waste pickers to represent themselves and communicate key environmental messages to a wider audience (European Commission, 2020).

The primary objective of the DMA is to educate, both the population in general and common interest groups, about waste management practices and circular economy principles while amplifying the voices of waste pickers (Wilson et al., 2012). The app integrates AI-generated personas developed in collaboration with waste pickers, ensuring a participatory approach that enhances social inclusion and knowledge dissemination (Gutberlet, 2015).

The key goals of the DMA application project include:

- Providing accessible environmental education through interactive digital content (Baldé et al., 2017),
- Encouraging behavioral change by engaging users with AI-driven storytelling techniques (Gunkel, 2020),
- Strengthening the role of waste pickers by using digital personas to share their expertise and lived experiences (Dias, 2016),
- Fostering community-driven solutions for sustainable waste management and circular economy adoption (Kirchherr et al., 2017).

The DMA app is specifically designed for implementation within waste picker cooperatives, focusing on C₁T₁T₂C₂, key elements of sustainable waste management (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2019).

The DMA is expected to contribute significantly to environmental education and digital inclusion, particularly among marginalized waste picker communities (Dias, 2016). By leveraging AI to facilitate participatory design, the project aims to:

- Empower waste pickers by giving them an active role in sustainability education (Wilson et al., 2012),
- Increase environmental awareness and responsible waste disposal habits among the population and common interest groups (Tilbury, 2011),
- Improve waste management efficiency through enhanced knowledge-sharing and community-driven solutions (Baldé et al., 2017),
- Support policy advocacy efforts by using AI-generated personas to highlight the challenges and contributions of waste pickers (Scholz et al., 2018).

The Digital Mobilizer App (DMA) is designed as a public-facing educational tool to enhance environmental awareness and promote sustainable development through waste separation. By integrating AI-generated personas created in collaboration with waste pickers, DMA aims to transfer the traditional role of street mobilizers into a dynamic digital platform. These personas, including adult and child representations, serve as relatable characters to guide users through interactive content on proper waste disposal practices, contamination risks, and circular economy principles. The app emphasizes inclusive representation, with waste pickers actively co-creating digital characters that reflect their realities and promote behavioral change among the general population.

At the current stage, the DMA remains in its preparatory and conceptual phase. The foundational design and persona development took place during a participatory workshop at the Waste Summit Brasília 2025, involving ten waste pickers from CENTCOOP. Full-scale development of the application is scheduled to begin in the second semester of 2025, led by students and researchers from UnB, AAU, and Saxion University. This upcoming phase will include prototype construction, user interface design, educational content creation, and pilot testing with diverse user groups to ensure impact, usability, and potential for policy advocacy.

3 The Workshop as the Starting Point of the MDA Project

DMA initial conceptualization resulted from a participatory workshop held during the Waste Summit Brasília 2025. The workshop was designed to engage waste pickers in both, identification and preliminary characterization of problems related to $C_1T_1T_2C_2$ and the development of AI-generated personas that accurately reflect their experiences and aspirations, ensuring inclusivity in environmental education (Gutberlet, 2015).

The methodology employed in the workshop followed a qualitative and participatory approach, where waste pickers were actively involved in discussions, persona creation, and problem identification related to their daily activities (Scholz et al., 2018). The process aimed to foster collaborative decision-making and co-design principles, reinforcing the idea that waste pickers should have agency over their representation in digital platforms (Dias, 2016).

3.1 Methodology

The workshop methodology was based on semi-structured interviews, focus groups, and interactive AI-based persona generation. The process unfolded in the following steps:

- Discussion on Representation: Waste pickers were encouraged to express how they wanted to be represented by AI, ensuring that digital personas reflected their identity, aspirations, and lived experiences (Gunkel, 2020),
- Persona Creation: AI technology from the Educado, another Egalitarian project was used to generate digital personas based on waste pickers' inputs. This participatory design approach enabled waste pickers to provide direct feedback on persona accuracy (Kang et al., 2021),
- Feedback and Adjustments: Participants evaluated the personas and provided suggestions for improvements, ensuring that the final representations were authentic and empowering (Scholz et al., 2018),
- Problem Identification and preliminary characterization: Participants highlighted the main challenges in waste collection, such as contamination, unsafe working conditions, and lack of public awareness (Wilson et al., 2012).

The workshop's methodology was designed to be iterative, meaning that personas could be refined and adjusted based on participant feedback over time (Gutberlet, 2015). It is worthwhile to emphasize that the problem identification and preliminary characterization activities were performed during the time the AI program was generating the personas.

3.1.1 Role and Profile of the Participants

The workshop brought together waste pickers, supervising professors, and students from three universities, each contributing to different aspects of the research process.

3.1.1.1 Waste Pickers

A total of seven women and three men from the CENTCOOP network of waste picker cooperatives participated in the workshop. They were asked to provide insights on how they wanted to be represented by the AI program and responded to questions about their future goals and the main challenges of waste collection (Dias, 2016).

Their contributions were essential in shaping the personas, ensuring that the AI-generated characters reflected real-life experiences and addressed key issues within the waste management ecosystem (Wilson et al., 2012).

3.1.1.2 Supervising Professors

Professors from the University of Brasília (UnB) guided the students and assisted with translations. Their responsibilities included:

- Ensuring that the questions posed to waste pickers aligned with the project's research objectives (Tilbury, 2011),
- Helping to bridge the communication gap between international students and local waste pickers (Gutberlet, 2015),
- Providing academic oversight to ensure methodological rigor (Scholz et al., 2018).

3.1.1.3 Students

Students from Aalborg University (AAU) and Saxion University were responsible for conducting interviews with waste pickers, with the support of UnB professors for translation and methodological guidance. Their roles included:

- AAU and Saxion students: Conducted interviews and structured discussion sessions, ensuring that waste pickers' insights were fully explored (Dias, 2016),
- UnB students: Assisted in persona generation and translations, helping to adapt AI-generated characters to better reflect waste pickers' identities (Kang et al., 2021).

This collaborative approach ensured that all participants played an active role in the research process, leading to more accurate, inclusive, and community-driven outcomes (Gunkel, 2020).

4 Results

The participatory workshop conducted during the Waste Summit Brasília 2025 provided valuable insights into the perspectives, challenges, and aspirations of waste pickers. The findings from this engagement were critical in shaping the development of the Digital Mobilizer App (DMA) and reinforcing the importance of AI-generated personas as a tool for environmental education and social representation.

These insights were gathered through a combination of ethnographic methods, participatory design techniques, and direct input from waste pickers, including written reflections during the workshop. This section presents the main findings from the visit, discussing their implications for the project.

4.1 Key Findings from the Workshop

The results obtained during the workshop reinforced several key themes that are central to the design and implementation of the DMA project:

- Presence of hospital waste in recycling streams, which poses severe health risks,
- Low-quality recyclables, making the sorting process less efficient and reducing the economic value of collected materials,
- Organic waste improperly mixed with recyclables, complicating the sorting process and generating additional waste,
- Unexpected hazardous materials, such as animal carcasses, which create unsanitary working conditions.

These findings highlight the need for better segregation at the source, as well as public awareness campaigns to educate households and businesses on proper waste disposal practices.

4.2 Representation Through AI-Generated Personas

One of the most innovative outcomes of the workshop was the strong engagement with the AI-generated personas. Waste pickers enthusiastically interacted with the digital characters, providing constructive feedback and even naming the personas based on real people they knew. This response highlighted how realistic and relatable the AI-generated personas were, reinforcing their potential as engagement tools for environmental education.

A key takeaway from this process was that waste pickers wanted to see themselves accurately represented—not only in terms of physical appearance but also in personality and attitude. The reactions to each persona illustrate how AI-generated representations can be refined through participatory feedback, ensuring that they resonate with the intended audience.

4.2.1 First Persona – Older Man (Initial Version Perceived as Too Serious)

The first AI-generated image (Figure 1) presented an older man who was perceived as too serious by the waste pickers. While they appreciated the effort, they felt that the persona's facial expression and demeanor did not fully capture their reality. The initial representation seemed distant, prompting discussions about the importance of warmth and relatability in AI-generated characters.

4.2.2 Second Persona – Woman (Minor Adjustments Required)

The second image (Figure 2), depicting a middle-aged woman, was well received but required small adjustments to better align with the waste pickers' expectations. The group suggested minor refinements to facial features and expressions, emphasizing that the persona should appear approachable and familiar. After these modifications, the waste pickers felt the persona accurately reflected someone from their community.

Figure 1-First image of a man generated

Figure 2. First image of a woman generated

4.2.3 Third Persona – Refined Older Man, Named "Roberto"

Based on the feedback from the first image, a corrected version of the older man was generated. This time, the waste pickers responded positively, noting that the new persona closely resembled someone they knew. They affectionately named him Roberto (Figure 3), solidifying the persona's acceptance as a representation of their reality. This moment underscored how adjustments in AI-generated images can significantly impact how they are perceived.

4.2.4 Fourth Persona – Woman, Named "Dona Ana"

The fourth image featured a woman whom the waste pickers instantly related to. They enthusiastically named her "Dona Ana" (Figure 4), a title reflecting respect and familiarity. This strong connection demonstrated how

AI-generated personas, when done right, can evoke an emotional response and foster a sense of ownership and representation.

4.2.5 Fifth and Sixth Personas – AI-Generated Children, Named "Aninha" and "Robertinho"

A defining moment of the workshop was the creation of child personas, a suggestion of the waste pickers. They asked for two children, which were generated and named "Aninha" (Little Ana) and "Robertinho" (Little Roberto). The reaction was overwhelmingly positive and emotional—waste pickers compared these personas (Figures 5 & 6) to their own children, reinforcing the strong cultural and emotional significance of these representations.

Figure 3. "Roberto"

Figure 4. "Dona Ana"

Figure 5. "Aninha"

Figure 6. "Robertinho"

The waste pickers defended the idea of using child personas as AI-driven influencers, as they believe that child figures could be more effective in engaging the public regarding sustainability in family contexts as well as towards the engagement of other children. This aligns with the Egalitarian Semester Project at AAU findings, which showed that personas can serve as powerful advocacy tools for marginalized communities.

4.3 Need for Systemic Changes

The workshop also revealed the waste pickers' perspectives on systemic improvements, emphasizing the importance of:

- Stronger enforcement of fines for improper waste disposal,
- Educational initiatives targeting businesses and households to improve sorting practices,
- Advocacy for policy changes to recognize the role of waste pickers in formal waste management strategies.

These findings support the idea that the DMA project should not only serve as an educational tool but also as a mechanism for broader advocacy efforts to improve waste management policies.

4.4 Implications for the DMA Project

The results of the workshop have direct implications for the next phase of the DMA development:

- Content Development: The AI-generated personas should be designed to educate users about contamination issues and other best practices for waste sorting,
- Engagement Strategies: The use of child personas as influencers should be explored further, as suggested by the waste pickers,
- Policy Integration: The DMA should include educational content that advocates for policy changes, aligning with the systemic improvements proposed during the workshop.

These findings align with research on participatory waste management, reinforcing the importance of co-designing tools with waste pickers to enhance their visibility and social impact (Rahman Rabbi et al., 2024).

4.5 Preliminary validation of results

UnB professors and students went to another cooperative in Brasilia (Recicla Mais), where they presented the DMA's results (Figures 3 to 6) and ideas to a real-life mobilizer, a waste picker, and an administrative person. Besides suggesting some minor modifications on the personas generated at CENTCOOP, the three Recicla Mais people recognized DMA's potential to generate real and meaningful impact within their community and expressed strong interest in future DMA workshops related to content creation as well as the generation of new personas and the corresponding avatars.

5 Work to be Done by Students During the Year of 2025

During the first semester of 2025, students from UnB, Aalborg University (AAU), and Saxion University will collaborate to transform the DMA from a conceptual model into a functional prototype aimed at educating the population in general and interest groups, on waste management. While initially inspired by the experiences of waste pickers, the DMA is designed to be a public-facing platform, encouraging broader societal engagement with sustainability and circular economy principles. Additionally, the DMA will serve as a proof of concept to be presented to government authorities, with the objective of securing public incentives and policy support for improved waste management initiatives.

One of the primary tasks for the students will be refining the AI-generated personas, ensuring that they accurately represent the diversity of waste management stakeholders. The feedback from waste pickers during future workshops will be incorporated to enhance the realism and relatability of the personas, making them appealing and trustworthy for a broader audience. The characters, including "Roberto", "Dona Ana", "Aninha", and "Robertinho", will be fine-tuned to effectively communicate sustainability concepts and act as engaging digital guides within the app. Additionally, the AI speech synthesis system will be improved to create natural-sounding voices, enhancing the user experience and making the interaction more immersive.

Alongside persona refinement, students will work on developing the DMA framework, ensuring it is intuitive and engaging for the population. The platform will feature a user-friendly interface that allows individuals to explore different aspects of waste management, interact with AI-driven storytelling, and participate in gamified learning experiences. DMA will also incorporate interactive challenges, quizzes, and rewards to encourage users to actively engage with recycling, waste reduction, and proper disposal practices in their daily lives.

A major focus of the project will be creating compelling educational content that resonates with the broader population. Using AI-driven narratives, the app will present real-world waste management scenarios, showing how individual actions contribute to a more sustainable society. The learning modules will be structured according to internationally recognized sustainability frameworks, including the P3RD model (P-Prevention, R₁-Reduction, R₂-Reuse, R₃-Recycling, and D-Disposal), an adaptation of the 10R Dutch Circular Economy framework, ensuring that users receive accurate and impactful information. In addition, the app will feature personalized recommendations, allowing users to track their learning progress and receive actionable tips on how to improve their waste management habits.

To validate the effectiveness of the app and gather critical feedback, pilot testing will be conducted with a diverse group of users, including students, professionals, families, and environmental advocates. These test sessions will assess engagement levels, usability, and knowledge retention, ensuring that the platform effectively motivates behavioral change regarding waste disposal and recycling. The feedback collected will guide further refinements before wider public deployment.

Beyond the technical and educational aspects, students will also focus on leveraging the app as a tool for policy advocacy. The goal is to use the data and insights gathered from public interactions with the platform to

demonstrate its potential impact on waste management at a societal level. This information will be compiled into reports and presentations advocating for incentive programs and regulatory changes that support sustainable waste management practices.

By the end of the year, the objective is to have a DMA functional public prototype, equipped with engaging AI personas, interactive sustainability lessons, and a foundation for publicity and policy discussions.

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